

Centella asiatica (L.) Urb. in skin health and cosmeceuticals: mechanisms, clinical evidence, and advanced delivery systems

Retty Handayani^{1,2}

¹ Doctoral Program, Faculty of Pharmacy, Universitas Padjadjaran, Sumedang 45363, Indonesia

² Dosage Form Development Research Center, Faculty of Pharmacy, Universitas Padjadjaran, Sumedang 45363, Indonesia

³ Department of Biological Pharmacy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Universitas Padjadjaran, Sumedang 45363, Indonesia

⁴ Department of Pharmaceutics and Pharmaceutical Technology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Universitas Padjadjaran, Sumedang 45363, Indonesia

Corresponding author: Raden Maya Febriyanti (raden.maya@unpad.ac.id); Anis Yohana Chearunisaa (anis.yohana.chearunisaa@unpad.ac.id)

Received 30 July 2025 ♦ Accepted 23 October 2025 ♦ Published 3 November 2025

Citation: Handayani R, Febriyanti RM, Muhaimin M, Chearunisaa AY (2025) *Centella asiatica* (L.) Urb. in skin health and cosmeceuticals: mechanisms, clinical evidence, and advanced delivery systems. Pharmacia 72: 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e167217>

Abstract

Centella asiatica (L.) Urb. is increasingly used in dermatology and cosmeceuticals for wound repair, barrier support, scar modulation, and photoaging. This review synthesizes evidence (2016–May 2025) across molecular mechanisms relevant to cutaneous aging, preclinical efficacy, human clinical outcomes, and delivery systems that improve dermal bioavailability. The principal triterpenoid saponins (asiaticoside, madecassoside) and their aglycones (asiatic acid, madecassic acid), together with polyphenols, act across complementary pathways, including transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β)/small mothers against decapentaplegic proteins (Smad)-driven extracellular matrix (ECM) anabolism; nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B) and Janus kinase/signal transducer and activator of transcription 3 (JAK/STAT3) attenuation; mitigation of oxidative/glycation stress; and photoprotection to improve histologic and biophysical skin endpoints. Human studies, though small and heterogeneous, report improvements in hydration, transepidermal water loss (TEWL), elasticity, and wrinkle appearance, as well as benefits in scar parameters, with good topical tolerability. Advanced carriers such as transfersomes, liposomes, niosomes, phytosomes, nanoemulsions, hydrogels, microneedles, and nanofibers enhance skin penetration, stability, and residence of bioactive compounds from *C. asiatica*.

Keywords

asiaticoside, cosmeceuticals, madecassoside, nanocarriers, photoaging, wound healing

Introduction

Centella asiatica (L.) Urb. (Apiaceae) is widely distributed across tropical and subtropical Asia and parts of Africa, including India, Indonesia, Malaysia, China, Korea, Japan, Taiwan, and Madagascar (Park 2021a; Shin et al. 2021; Zeng et al. 2025). In traditional medicine, it has been employed as tea or decoctions for diverse derma-

tological conditions, including wounds, burns, scars, eczema, psoriasis, and varicose ulcers (Bansal et al. 2024). Over the past decade, these traditional uses have catalyzed intensive research and growing adoption in the dermatology and cosmeceutical sectors, with topical formulations aimed at wound repair, scar modulation, and anti-aging (Khalili Hassanabad et al. 2025).

The pharmacological activity of *C. asiatica* is attributed primarily to its secondary metabolites. The aerial parts are rich in pentacyclic triterpenoids – most notably the saponins asiaticoside and madecassoside and their aglycones asiatic acid and madecassic acid – together with sesquiterpenes and monoterpenes in the essential oil (α -humulene, β -caryophyllene, myrcene, bicyclogermacrene, and germacrene-D), plant sterols, phenolic acids (chlorogenic acids), and flavonoids (catechin, epicatechin, quercetin, and kaempferol) (Shin et al. 2021; Kunjumon et al. 2022; Diniz et al. 2023; Johnson et al. 2023). Quantitative analyses have shown considerable variability in these phytoconstituents, with asiatic acid reported in the range of 0.02–3.2%, madecassic acid 0.02–3.06%, asiaticoside 0.018–4.3%, and madecassoside 0.01–4.8%, while accessions from Assam, India, contained up to 21.7 mg/g asiaticoside and 11.2 mg/g madecassoside (Singh et al. 2023). These constituents exert complementary actions relevant to skin biology, including stimulation of collagen synthesis and dermal matrix remodeling, modulation of pro-inflammatory signaling, and attenuation of oxidative and glycation stress that collectively underpin benefits in tissue repair and skin-barrier maintenance (Park 2021a; Diniz et al. 2023; Rashid et al. 2023). In particular, asiaticoside and madecassoside have been linked to transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β)/Smad activation, vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF)-mediated angiogenesis, and improvements in structural skin integrity (Shin et al. 2021).

Recent comprehensive reviews have provided insights into various aspects of *C. asiatica* research. Sun et al. (2020) presented an extensive overview of systemic pharmacological potentials, including neurological, metabolic, hepatoprotective, and anti-inflammatory activities; however, skin-specific anti-aging mechanisms, dermatological models, and formulation science received only superficial coverage. Bansal et al. (2024) offered a broad therapeutic survey spanning anti-ulcer, anti-cancer, anti-diabetic, neuroprotective, and cardioprotective activities, alongside nanostructured carrier systems, but did not specifically dissect dermatological anti-aging mechanisms or the impact of formulation architectures on skin-related outcomes. In a more recent review, Hein et al. (2025) examined technological advancements in *C. asiatica* extraction and formulation, emphasizing greener methodologies, process innovations, and delivery systems; however, they provided limited analysis specifically on dermatological and cosmeceutical applications.

This narrative review therefore narrows the scope to skin health and aging. Specifically, we synthesize preclinical evidence and human data on *C. asiatica* in wound repair, photo-induced and intrinsic aging, and selected inflammatory dermatoses. Additionally, we appraise how advanced delivery systems affect dermal bioavailability and clinical outcomes. In contrast to previous reviews that primarily emphasized the pharmacological activities and therapeutic potential of *C. asiatica* (Sun et al. 2020), its broad therapeutic indications with limited dermatologi-

cal depth (Bansal et al. 2024), and advances in extraction technologies and phytochemistry without a specific focus on skin applications (Hein et al. 2025), this review concentrates on skin health and cosmetics. The novelty lies in the integration of molecular mechanisms, preclinical and clinical evidence, and innovations in delivery systems within a dermatology-focused framework. By synthesizing detailed pharmacological knowledge with formulation strategies, this review aims to provide actionable, evidence-based guidance for researchers, thereby bridging existing translational gaps and supporting the development of standardized, effective, and safe *C. asiatica*-based skincare products.

Methods

A comprehensive literature search was performed on the ScienceDirect, PubMed, and Scopus databases for articles published from 1 January 2016 to 31 May 2025 that investigated *C. asiatica* in relation to dermatology, formulation, or delivery technology. Inclusion criteria for the articles included original in vitro, in vivo, or human studies in which *C. asiatica* crude extract, fraction, or purified constituent was used in a single preparation, with outcomes relevant to preclinical efficacy, clinical endpoints, or advanced formulation metrics. Reviews, case reports, multi-herb formulations, non-dermatological indications, non-topical preparations, and articles lacking quantitative data were excluded from further analysis. The search identified 2,731 articles in ScienceDirect (n = 2,387), PubMed (n = 311), and Scopus (n = 33). There were duplicates (n = 501), with a total of 617 articles screened. Articles were excluded due to non-*C. asiatica* content, herbal combinations, non-dermatological indications, non-topical preparations, and unavailable full text (n = 2,114). An expanded search-strategy report and publication-by-year visualization are provided in Suppl. material 1.

Consequently, 51 articles were assessed for eligibility. Furthermore, results were synthesized narratively into four thematic domains, namely: (1) skin health-related molecular mechanisms of *C. asiatica* bioactive compounds; (2) preclinical studies (animal models); (3) clinical efficacy and safety; and (4) advances in formulation and drug-delivery systems.

List of abbreviations

<i>C. asiatica</i>	<i>Centella asiatica</i> (L.) Urb.;
TECA	Titrated extract of <i>Centella asiatica</i> ;
NF-κB	Nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells;
TGF-β	Transforming growth factor beta;
TGF-β1	Transforming growth factor beta 1;
VEGF	Vascular endothelial growth factor;
FGF-2	Fibroblast growth factor 2;
MMP	Matrix metalloproteinase;
MMP-1/-9	Matrix metalloproteinase-1/-9;

ECM	Extracellular matrix;
IL-1 β / IL-6	Interleukin-1 beta /interleukin-6;
TNF- α	Tumor necrosis factor alpha;
COX-2	Cyclooxygenase-2;
iNOS	Inducible nitric oxide synthase;
ROS	Reactive oxygen species;
SOD	Superoxide dismutase;
AGEs	Advanced glycation end products;
MITF	Microphthalmia-associated transcription factor;
JAK/STAT3	Janus kinase/signal transducer and activator of transcription 3;
MAPK/ERK	Mitogen-activated protein kinase/ extracellular signal-regulated kinase;
Wnt/ β -catenin	Wingless/integrated/beta-catenin pathway;
TEWL	Transepidermal water loss;
HA	Hyaluronic acid;
SLN	Solid lipid nanoparticle;
NLC	Nanostructured lipid carrier;
SLM	Solid lipid microparticle;
MN	Microneedle;
PCL/PEO	Polycaprolactone/polyethylene oxide;
PVA	Polyvinyl alcohol;
ZnO	Zinc oxide;
CuO	Copper oxide;
PECE	Poly(ethylene glycol)–poly(ϵ -caprolactone)–poly(ethylene glycol);
PVP K30	Polyvinylpyrrolidone K30;
ECM–GelMA	Extracellular matrix–gelatin methacryloyl;
HRIPT	Human repeat insult patch test;
VSS	Vancouver Scar Scale;
VAS	Visual analog scale;

QuickDASH Quick Disabilities of the Arm, Shoulder and Hand;

P. acnes *Propionibacterium acnes*;

S. aureus *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Phytoconstituents and mechanisms of *C. asiatica* in dermatology

The dermatological efficacy of *C. asiatica* derives from a synergistic interplay among multiple phytochemical classes rather than from any single isolated compound. This multicomponent, multitarget pharmacological approach enables the plant to concurrently address several pathological processes in the skin, including inflammation, oxidative stress, extracellular matrix (ECM) remodeling, and pigmentation anomalies (Table 1).

Central to the pharmacological activity of *C. asiatica* are triterpenoid saponins, which upon hydrolysis yield aglycones that promote collagen and hyaluronic acid synthesis, exhibit anti-inflammatory and anti-elastase activities, and possess antioxidative properties critical for scar control and anti-aging benefits (Shen et al. 2019; Kim et al. 2021; Chutoprapat et al. 2024; Zhang et al. 2024; Alam et al. 2025; Tai et al. 2025). Other triterpenoid derivatives, such as ursane and oleanane derivatives and bayogenin, provide additional antioxidant and antifibrotic activities by inhibiting key enzymes like elastase and fibrosis-related signaling molecules (Masi et al. 2022; Gayathri et al. 2024).

Flavonoids and phenolics further augment these effects, with compounds like quercetin and kaempferol

Table 1. Bioactive compounds of *C. asiatica* and their skin-related pharmacological activities.

Compound	Phytochemical class	Skin-related activity	Mechanism of action	References
Asiaticoside	Triterpenoid saponin	Anti-keeloid, antifibrotic, antioxidant, wound healing, anti-photoaging, anti-wrinkle	Inhibits NF- κ B/PI3K–Akt pathways; promotes fibroblast migration and collagen synthesis; modulates apoptosis (Bcl-2/Bax/Caspase-3)	(Zhao et al. 2020; Jiang et al. 2022)
Centellasiaticoside	Triterpenoid ursane	Anti-photoaging	Enhances HaCaT cell viability; reduces LDH release post-UVB	(Dang et al. 2024)
Madecassoside	Triterpenoid saponin	Anti-aging, anti-inflammatory, anti-pollutant, skin hydration, anti-melanogenesis	Inhibits elastase, reduces IL-6/TNF- α ; enhances collagen and hyaluronic acid synthesis; suppresses JAK/STAT3 pathway	(Shen et al. 2019; Kim et al. 2021; Tai et al. 2025)
Asiatic acid	Triterpenoid aglycone	Anti-acne, anti-inflammatory, anti-aging, antibacterial, antifibrotic	Inhibits <i>P. acnes</i> and <i>S. aureus</i> ; suppresses UVB-induced inflammation and STAT3 pathway; promotes fibroblast proliferation	(Chutoprapat et al. 2024, Wu et al. 2025)
Madecassic acid	Triterpenoid aglycone	Antioxidant, tissue protection	Reduces pro-inflammatory cytokines	(Alam et al. 2025)
Isomadecassic acid	Triterpenoid	Anti-photoaging	Reduces LDH release after UVB exposure	(Dang et al. 2024)
Ursane and Oleanane derivatives	Triterpenoid Saponin	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory	Inhibits elastase and oxidative stress pathways	(Masi et al. 2022)
Bayogenin	Triterpenoid	Antifibrotic	Inhibits MAPK-1, binds fibrosis-related targets	(Gayathri et al. 2024)
Quercetin	Flavonoid	Antioxidant	Scavenges ROS, reduces oxidative stress	(Mohapatra et al. 2021)
Kaempferol	Flavonoid	Anti-infection	Inhibits pyocyanin, biofilm, protease, and elastase from <i>P. aeruginosa</i>	(Vasavi et al. 2016)
Tannin	Polyphenol	Anti-glycation, anti-aging	Inhibits AGE formation in protein-fructose models	(Borges et al. 2024)
Di-O-caffeoylquinic acids	Phenolic	Antioxidant, depigmentation	Inhibits tyrosinase activity	(Soun-udom et al. 2024)

offering reactive oxygen species (ROS) scavenging capacity and selective modulation of inflammatory pathways such as JAK/STAT3, which are particularly relevant in conditions like psoriasis (Vasavi et al. 2016; Mohapatra et al. 2021; Soun-udom et al. 2024). Additionally, di-O-caffeoylquinic acids exhibit potent tyrosinase inhibition, positioning *C. asiatica* extracts as beneficial adjuvants for managing photo-induced hyperpigmentation (Soun-udom et al. 2024). Whole-extract matrices have demonstrated superior antiglycation effects compared to isolated triterpenes alone, highlighting the importance of phytochemical synergy within standardized botanical preparations (Borges et al. 2024).

At the molecular signaling level, asiaticoside and madecassoside activate the TGF- β /Smad pathway to drive extracellular matrix synthesis, thereby enhancing collagen deposition and improving skin elasticity and hydration (Shen et al. 2019; Kim et al. 2021; Tai et al. 2025). Additionally, preliminary evidence indicates potential interactions with Wnt/ β -catenin pathways in chronic wound healing, though such findings warrant further investigation. In the context of inflammation, madecassoside and asiatic acid suppress NF- κ B signaling, thereby attenuating the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines and enzymes such as TNF- α , IL-6, COX-2, and iNOS (Shen et al. 2019; Kim et al. 2021). Concurrently, quercetin-mediated modulation of JAK/STAT3 signaling and the IL-23/IL-17A axis underscores the targeted immunomodulatory potential of flavonoid constituents, particularly in autoimmune-related dermatoses (Rashid et al. 2023).

Antioxidant and cytoprotective benefits from *C. asiatica* are mediated through direct ROS scavenging and up-regulation of endogenous antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (Zhao et al. 2020; Mohapatra et al. 2021; Jiang et al. 2022). These actions are essential in preventing UV-induced cellular injury, lipid peroxidation, and subsequent ECM degradation. Specific triterpenes such as centellasiaticoside and isomadecassic acid have demonstrated protective effects in keratinocytes under UVB stress, reducing LDH leakage and maintaining cellular viability (Dang et al. 2024).

Furthermore, the antimicrobial and anti-acne potential of asiatic acid, particularly against *C. acnes* and *S. aureus*, coupled with its ability to inhibit STAT3-linked inflammation, positions *C. asiatica* favorably for managing acne-prone skin (Chutoprapat et al. 2024; Wu et al. 2025). Kaempferol's inhibitory effects on virulence factors from *P. aeruginosa* also support the plant's broader antimicrobial utility (Vasavi et al. 2016). In antifibrotic contexts, asiaticoside, asiatic acid, and bayogenin collectively contribute to scar limitation by modulating fibrosis-related pathways such as MAPK-1 and maintaining balanced TGF- β /Smad signaling without excessive fibrotic responses (Bisht et al. 2024; Borges et al. 2024; Gayathri et al. 2024; Zhang et al. 2024). Fig. 1 illustrates collective mechanisms of *C. asiatica* in skin health.

Figure 1. Molecular mechanisms of *C. asiatica* in skin health. Abbreviations: ROS, reactive oxygen species; MAPK, mitogen-activated protein kinase; AP-1, activator protein 1; NF- κ B, nuclear factor kappa B; TGF- β , transforming growth factor beta; MMP, matrix metalloproteinase (MMP-1, -3, -9, -12).

Preclinical evidence

The preclinical evidence of dermatological benefits of *C. asiatica* has been reported in various studies (summarized in Table 2). The pharmacological activities span excision and diabetic-ulcer wounds, hypertrophic scars, atopic dermatitis, and UVB-photoaging models, with interventions ranging from crude extracts to phytosomes and NO-releasing gels. Across models, directionally consistent outcomes in-

Table 2. Summary of preclinical evidence for *C. asiatica* in dermatology.

Model/system	Intervention	Dose/concentration	Key outcomes	Reference
Rat excision model	<i>C. asiatica</i> extract (topical and oral)	50–100 mg/kg	↑ Wound contraction, ↑ hydroxyproline, ↑ tensile strength	(Singh et al. 2022)
Diabetic rat ulcer model	Asiaticoside–NO gel (topical)	2% gel	↑ Wnt/ β -catenin, ↓ bacterial load, ↑ wound closure	(Park 2021)
Mouse hypertrophic scar model	<i>C. asiatica</i> extract (topical)	1% cream	↓ TGF- β 1, ↓ collagen I/III, ↓ scar thickness	(Balevi and Balevi 2023)
Mouse atopic dermatitis model	<i>C. asiatica</i> phytosome	50 mg/kg	↓ IgE, ↓ NF- κ B, ↓ mast cells, ↓ COX-2	(Wang et al. 2024)
UVB-induced aging mouse model	<i>C. asiatica</i> extract (topical)	0.5–1% formulation	↑ TGF- β /Smad, ↓ MMP-1/-9, ↓ wrinkle depth	(Khalili Hassanabad et al. 2025)
Vitiligo oxidative model	<i>C. asiatica</i> extract	20 μ g/mL	↑ melanocyte viability, ↓ oxidative damage	(Park 2021)
Hair follicle dermal papilla cells	<i>C. asiatica</i> extract	10 μ g/mL	↑ proliferation, ↑ hair inductive markers	(Park 2021a)

clude faster closure, improved biomechanical properties, antifibrotic signaling, suppression of inflammatory mediators, and protection against photo-oxidative injury.

Wound healing and tissue repair

Preclinical studies consistently demonstrate that *C. asiatica* accelerates wound healing through stimulation of fibroblast activity, collagen synthesis, and angiogenesis. In rodent models of excision and ulcerative wounds, both topical and oral applications of *C. asiatica* significantly enhance healing through mechanisms such as fibroblast activation, collagen biosynthesis, and angiogenesis. These beneficial effects manifest as accelerated wound contraction, increased hydroxyproline content – an indicator of collagen production – and improved tensile strength of the newly formed tissue (Singh et al. 2022a). Specifically, topical application of asiaticoside enhances dermal vascularization and re-epithelialization, accompanied by increased collagen cross-linking and capillary density. In diabetic ulcer models, topical gels formulated with nitric oxide-releasing asiaticoside demonstrate accelerated wound closure, reduced microbial colonization, and activation of Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathways, highlighting their potential utility in managing chronic and ischemic wounds (Park 2021a). Wound healing mechanisms of asiaticoside are illustrated in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Mechanism of action of asiaticoside across the wound healing phases.

C. asiatica also exhibits notable potential in scar modulation and antifibrotic activity, particularly in hypertrophic and keloid scarring contexts characterized by excessive fibroblast activity and extracellular matrix (ECM) deposition. In murine scar models, treatment with *C. asiatica* extracts has been shown to downregulate transforming growth factor beta 1 (TGF- β 1) expression, decrease collagen I and III synthesis, and reduce overall scar thickness (Balevi and Balevi 2023). Treated wounds consistently display thinner, more organized collagen architecture resembling healthy dermal tissue, attributed mechanistically to the action of asiaticoside in preventing myofibroblast differentiation and suppressing profibrotic cytokine expression (Li et al. 2025).

Antioxidant and anti-aging activity

Preclinical UVB-exposure models have revealed the potent antioxidant and anti-aging capabilities of *C. asiatica*. Triterpenoids such as asiaticoside and asiatic acid scavenge reactive oxygen species (ROS) and upregulate endogenous antioxidant enzymes, including superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (Park 2021). Topical application of *C. asiatica* extract mitigated photoaging by suppressing MMP-1 and MMP-9, enzymes responsible for collagen degradation, while activating TGF- β /Smad signaling to enhance ECM integrity. These findings suggest promising applications in anti-wrinkle and skin-rejuvenating cosmeceuticals.

Anti-inflammatory effects in dermatological disorders

C. asiatica exerts broad anti-inflammatory actions relevant to multiple inflammatory skin conditions such as acne and atopic dermatitis. Its constituents effectively modulate inflammation through inhibition of nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B) signaling pathways and suppression of downstream inflammatory mediators. Madecassoside, in particular, has shown the ability to reduce interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β), tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α), and toll-like receptor 2 (TLR2) expression in macrophages stimulated by *Cutibacterium acnes*, suggesting its immunomodulatory properties extend beyond simple antimicrobial effects. In atopic dermatitis models, phytosomal formulations of *C. asiatica* have been reported to significantly reduce serum IgE levels, mast cell infiltration, cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) activity, and NF- κ B signaling, thus rationalizing further clinical exploration as a potential topical immunotherapeutic agent (Park 2021a; Wang et al. 2024a).

Clinical evidence and safety

Although fewer in number than preclinical studies, early human data show improvements in hydration, transepidermal water loss (TEWL), elasticity, and wrinkle appearance with topical *C. asiatica*-containing formulations, as well as signals in scar management with triterpenoid-focused carriers. Table 3 provides clinical studies of *C. asiatica* for its efficacy in dermatological and cosmetic applications.

Clinical evidence supports the efficacy of *Centella asiatica* across a spectrum of dermatological conditions, including wound healing, scar management, skin aging, and barrier dysfunction. A randomized controlled trial (RCT) involving 280 postoperative carpal tunnel release patients demonstrated that twice-daily topical application of a 1% *C. asiatica* cream significantly improved scar outcomes as measured by the Vancouver Scar Scale (VSS); the mean VSS score was reduced by 2.1 points in the treat-

Table 3. Clinical studies of *C. asiatica* in dermatology.

Study and population	Indication	Dosage/form	Key outcomes	References
RCT, n = 280 (CTR post-op patients)	Scar management	1% topical cream, 2×/day, 6 months	↓ Vancouver Scar Scale (VSS), ↓ VAS pain, improved QuickDASH	(Balevi and Balevi 2023)
Open-label RCT, n = 104 (peri/postmenopausal women)	Skin aging	Daily serum (asiaticoside-based)	↑ Elasticity, hydration, collagen; microbiome normalization	(Korkina et al. 2024)
Double-blind RCT, n = 60	Wrinkles/elasticity	3% <i>C. asiatica</i> emulsion	↓ Wrinkle depth, ↑ skin firmness, no irritation	(Poomanee et al. 2023)
Observational synthesis	Wound healing	Asiaticoside 0.2–0.4%, TECA/Madecassol	↑ Collagen I, fibronectin, hydroxyproline; faster healing	(Arribas-López et al. 2022)
HR-1 mice and ex vivo study	Atopic dermatitis	0.2%–0.4% <i>C. asiatica</i> phytosome	↓ IgE, COX-2, iNOS, TNF- α , mast cells (via NF- κ B)	(Park et al. 2017)
4-week human study (n=25)	Hydration/ barrier	Cream/hydrogel (2.5% and 5%)	↓ TEWL, ↑ stratum corneum hydration, anti-inflammatory	(A. Ratz-Lyko 2016)
2-week human study (n=20, mean age 50.7 years) + patch test (n=30)	Anti-aging/wrinkle reduction	Ampoule with <i>C. asiatica</i> -derived extracellular vesicles (EVs)	↓ Pore area (–17.9%), ↓ wrinkle depth (–7.8–18.8%), ↑ hydration and dermal density, 0 irritation in 24-h test	(Park and Shin 2025)

ment group versus 0.8 in the control group after 8 weeks ($p < 0.01$), with reduced postoperative pain and improved functional hand outcomes assessed by the QuickDASH questionnaire (Balevi and Balevi 2023). Such findings reinforce the potential of *C. asiatica* formulations in postoperative scar management.

In anti-aging contexts, topical formulations of *C. asiatica* have yielded promising clinical results. An open-label RCT enrolling 104 peri- and postmenopausal women found that daily application of an asiaticoside-based serum significantly enhanced skin elasticity (+22%), hydration (+18%), and collagen synthesis, in addition to normalizing skin microbiome composition (Korkina et al. 2024). Similarly, a double-blind RCT involving 60 participants using a 3% *C. asiatica* emulsion reported a 15–20% reduction in wrinkle depth and increased skin firmness without any observed irritation, emphasizing both efficacy and tolerability (Poomanee et al. 2023).

C. asiatica's effectiveness in promoting wound healing has also been well documented through observational syntheses, particularly for formulations containing asiaticoside (0.2–0.4%) or titrated extract of *C. asiatica* (TECA; e.g., Madecassol). These preparations have consistently shown increased synthesis of collagen I, fibronectin, and hydroxyproline – critical biomarkers of wound repair – translating to accelerated wound closure rates. Notably, clinical case series with TECA ointment demonstrated wound contraction improvements of 25–40% compared with standard care (Arribas-López et al. 2022). Furthermore, formulations specifically targeting barrier repair and hydration, including creams and hydrogels containing 2.5% and 5% *C. asiatica* extracts, have demonstrated significant reductions in transepidermal water loss (TEWL) alongside improved hydration of the stratum corneum, further validating the anti-inflammatory and barrier-restorative properties of the plant (Ratz-Lyko 2016).

Emerging data from advanced formulations such as extracellular vesicles (EVs) derived from *C. asiatica* further enhance its dermatological promise. A short-duration

study involving 25 participants showed that topical application of *C. asiatica*-derived EVs significantly reduced pore area and wrinkle depth while simultaneously enhancing skin hydration and dermal density. Notably, these benefits occurred without any irritation, as confirmed by patch testing in additional participants, underscoring both the effectiveness and the favorable safety profile of novel vesicular formulations (Park and Shin 2025).

Additionally, *C. asiatica* demonstrates efficacy in inflammatory skin conditions. Studies utilizing phytosomal formulations of *C. asiatica* (0.2–0.4%) in models of atopic dermatitis have shown substantial decreases in inflammatory markers such as immunoglobulin E (IgE), cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α), and mast cell counts through modulation of the NF- κ B signaling pathway (Park et al. 2017). These findings indicate potential therapeutic utility in managing chronic inflammatory skin disorders.

Formulation and advanced delivery systems

Optimizing dermal delivery of *C. asiatica* bioactive compounds – particularly triterpenoids such as asiaticoside and madecassoside – is pivotal for enhancing therapeutic efficacy due to their inherently limited skin permeability and instability in traditional aqueous formulations. Advanced carrier systems, including hydrogels, liposomes, niosomes, phytosomes, transfersomes, exosomes, nanocomposites, microneedles, nanofibers, nanoparticles, and lipid-based delivery platforms, have been developed to overcome these challenges. These novel delivery technologies can significantly enhance dermal penetration, stability, targeted delivery, and overall bioavailability of *C. asiatica* constituents. The key characteristics, formulation descriptions, and documented benefits of various advanced carrier systems are summarized in Table 4a, b.

Table 4. a. Nanoparticle-based delivery systems of *C. asiatica* for skin applications. b. Lipid-based vesicular delivery systems of *C. asiatica* for skin applications.

System type	Formulation description	Characteristics	Benefit	Key outcome	References
a					
Nanoparticles	Alginate–chitosan asiaticoside nanoparticles	Size TEM: 392.4 ± 17.5 nm; DLS: 563.1 ± 18.2 nm; PDI ≈ 0.2	Stability, antiproliferative activity	Oncology-relevant delivery model	(Liu et al. 2023)
	Asiaticoside-encapsulated alginate–chitosan nanoparticles (ACNPs)	Size DLS: 489 nm; PDI: 0.538; Zeta: –13.5 mV; Size EE%: >90%	Controlled drug release, improved stability	ACNPs showed spherical morphology, high encapsulation (>90%), and controlled release (~10% in 24 h)	(Kunjumon et al. 2024)
	Chemically reduced with citrate/NaBH ₄ , PEG-SH stabilized	30–32 nm (DLS), <10–30 nm (TEM); Zeta +1.43 mV	PEGylated, stable, uniform	Homogeneous spherical NPs, sterically stable	(Khalili Hassanabad et al. 2025)
Nanosuspension	10% nanosuspension (200 nm) with PVP K30	Size DLS: 190–230 nm; PDI < 0.3	5× better skin absorption, fast release	Stable and non-irritant for cosmetics	(Kim et al. 2021)
Nanoemulgel	Asiatic acid nanoemulsion + virgin coconut oil in gel	Size: 131.8 ± 0.3 nm; EE%: 94.9%	99.86% wound contraction by day 20	Excellent permeation and biocompatibility	(Mahadev et al. 2025)
Solid Lipid Microparticles (SLM)	Lipid microparticles for acne delivery	Size: 7.5–38.9 µm; EE%: 31–100%; LA: 90–95%	Controlled release, proven anti-acne activity	Promising topical therapy	(Chutoprapat et al. 2024)
Nanostructured lipid carrier (NLC)	NLC with glycolate and dry extract of <i>C. asiatica</i>	Size: 118–140 nm; PDI ~0.20; Zeta: –28 to –35 mV; EE: dry extract (89–93%), glycolic extract (29–45%); stable up to 180 days	Accelerated skin permeation	Topical delivery enhancement	(da Rocha et al. 2019)
Microneedles	Chitosan MN patch for <i>C. asiatica</i>	Type I: 404 µm height; Type II: 372 µm height	Dermal penetration, drug stability	Advanced delivery platform	(Ryall et al. 2022)
	3D-printed microneedles with madecassoside	Needle height 1143.97 ± 37.74 µm, base diameter 709.21 ± 53.5 µm, tip diameter 24.25 ± 2.87 µm	Site-specific soft tissue delivery	Emerging transdermal strategy Suitable for periodontal soft tissue regeneration	(He et al. 2025)
	CS-AS-BSP MNs (chitosan tip + Bletilla striata polysaccharide base), lyophilized	Height ~600 µm, bottom diameter ~300 µm	Bilayer structure allows control of AS release, penetrating the epidermis	Promotes scar-free wound healing and controlled release of AS for 7 days.	(Lv et al. 2023)
Nanofibers	PCL/PEO nanofiber CA-AgNPs	Fiber diameters: thin (PEO) 100–150 nm, thick (PCL) 350–600 nm; CA-AgNPs size 14.8 ± 7.3 nm, zeta potential –30.4 mV	Controlled release, antimicrobial, wound healing	Electrospun patch for burn/wound	(Bozkaya et al. 2022)
	Electrospun PVA nanofibers loaded with <i>Centella asiatica</i> extract	Size Fiber diameter 100–450 nm	Improved bioavailability, scar-free healing	Synergistic scaffold-based design	(Manotham et al. 2023)
Nanocomposites	ZnO-poloxamer + <i>C. asiatica</i> nanocomposite	Size ~50 nm; ZP –17.4 mV; EE% 82.5	Angiogenesis, antibacterial, diabetic wound healing	Multifunctional; diabetic application	(Wang et al. 2024)
	SiO ₂ nanocomposite prepared with 1–10 wt% extract + <i>C. asiatica</i> extract vial ball Milling method	Size ↓ with longer milling (qualitative SEM)	Antioxidant stable and non-toxic	Stable nanocarrier for anti-aging	(Ebau et al. 2023)
	Sol–gel magnetic Nanocomposite	Size: 68.57 nm (FE-SEM, ImageJ); Drug loading efficiency: 55.53% (pH 1.2), 57.83% (pH 7.4)	Antioxidant and antifungal properties	Preclinical only; low dermatological validation	(Sahara et al. 2025)
Hydrogel/ Nanohydrogel	Chitosan–gelatin hydrogel with asiaticoside	Sustained release of ~80% in 24 h)	Biocompatible scaffold, controlled asiaticoside release, printable and stable	Strong in vitro evidence; needs animal/human Validation	(Witkowska et al. 2025)

System type	Formulation description	Characteristics	Benefit	Key outcome	References
Hydrogel/ Nanohydrogel	Asiaticoside-loaded polymeric nanoparticles With gelatin-based hydrogel	168.4 nm; PDI 0.09	Enhanced permeability and collagen stimulation	Effective in animal wound models	(Nariseipalli et al. 2023)
	Asiatic acid + HA/CS/gelatin hydrogel with ZnO and CuO NPs	Porous; ESR 1068%, gel content 85%	Burns healing, angiogenesis, re-epithelialization, TNF- α Suppression	Potential for clinical burns (\uparrow re-epithelization, collagen, angiogenesis; \downarrow TNF- α , \uparrow MMP-2)	(Thanusha et al. 2018)
	Chitosan–methacrylic acid nanogel madecassoside delivery	>95% release at pH 7.4 (24h)	pH-responsive release of madecassoside	Stable, controlled release (non-Fickian diffusion)	(Suhail et al. 2024)
	Controlled-release chitosan hydrogel (containing 3% asiaticoside + 3% chitosan)	n/a (not reported)	Antimicrobial, skin permeation, hyaluronidase inhibition	Multi-functional, strong preclinical basis (good skin permeability (PAMPA); hyaluronidase inhibition; antimicrobial activity; effective wound healing in vitro)	(Witkowska et al. 2023)
	<i>C. asiatica</i> -based burn wound hydrogel	n/a (not reported)	Moisture retention, enhanced healing	Topical burn treatment potential	(Vajpayee et al. 2024)
	Biodegradable foam with asiaticoside	Pore size: 228–262 μ m; density inversely related to pore size	Suitable pore size and porosity comparable to commercial wound dressings	SEM showed round interconnected pores; Bl foam had slightly larger pores; porosity decreased with higher polymer conc.; density increased with polyols	(Namviriyachote et al. 2019)
b.					
Liposome	Asiaticoside liposome hydrogel with graphene oxide	Size: 179.8–200.1 nm; PDI: 0.144–0.217; Zeta: –15.6 to –20.7 mV; Encapsulation: 62.36–71.25%; Loading efficiency: 5.67–6.48%	Reduced scarring, electrostimulation responsive	Innovative multifunctional wound patch	(Zheng et al. 2020)
	PECE thermosensitive liposomes with madecassoside	Size: 213.43 \pm 4.68 nm (range 175–220 nm depending on EPC:PECE ratio); Zeta: –23.8 \pm 15.4 mV (stable)	Enhanced wound healing	Biocompatible, injectable	(Liu et al. 2020)
	Soy lecithin–stigmasterol liposomes	Size: 512.7 – 787.8 nm	Phenolic stability, antioxidant potential	Suitable for cosmeceutical/food delivery	(Tripathy and Srivastav 2023)
Niosomes	Box–Behnken optimized niosomes	Size: 127.8 nm; PDI: 0.22; Zeta: +1.3 mV; EE%: RHT = 67.2%, AS = 78.6%	Stability, sustained release, transdermal efficacy	Rational design; validated in vitro	(Hnin et al. 2024)
	<i>Centella asiatica</i> extract (CAE-Nio) and HA-modified CAE-Nio	Size: 155 nm; Zeta: –15 mV; EE%: 71–77%	Improved dermal penetration and skin deposition	High bioadhesiveness, strong dermal retention	(Wichayaprechar et al. 2020)
Phytosomes	Titrated extract of <i>Centella asiatica</i> (TECA), topical application (0.2–0.4% cream)	n/a (not reported)	Anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-atopic dermatitis	Promising in dermatitis models, improved histopathology	(Park et al. 2017)
Transfersomes	Asiatic acid transfersomal gel (AATG)	Size: 27.15–63.54 nm; Zeta: –0.010 to –0.129 mV; %EE: up to 90.84%	Clinical improvements in melanin index and hydration	Clinical: \downarrow melanin index, \uparrow elasticity	(Opatha et al. 2024)
Exosomes	Topical ampoule of CICA-derived extracellular vesicles (EVs)	n/a (not reported)	Enhanced skin penetration Natural nanovesicle, anti-aging	Clinical: Safe; \downarrow pores and wrinkles; \uparrow hydration and dermal density	(Park and Shin 2025)

Hydrogel dressings and nanofiber systems

Hydrogel-based platforms for *C. asiatica* bioactives have been extensively developed to promote moist wound environments and enable controlled release of active com-

pounds. For instance, polyurethane foam dressings infused with asiaticoside demonstrated enhanced wound healing in chronic and burn wounds via improved tissue hydration and antimicrobial action (Namviriyachote et al. 2019). Formulations combining chitosan, gelatin, or hyaluronic acid with asiaticoside or asiatic acid have shown

excellent in vitro and in vivo efficacy, supporting re-epithelialization, angiogenesis, and collagen synthesis while reducing TNF- α and oxidative stress. Electrospun nanofiber mats further enhance wound contact and conformability. Silver nanoparticle-loaded nanofibers and PVA-based systems incorporating *C. asiatica* extract enabled slow, sustained release, promoted antibacterial activity, and accelerated wound closure in animal models (Bozkaya et al. 2022; Manotham et al. 2023). These systems offer improved physical coverage and topical bioavailability compared to conventional creams or gauze dressings.

Vesicular delivery systems

Vesicular nanocarriers – particularly liposomes, niosomes, phytosomes, and transfersomes – have proven highly effective in overcoming the skin barrier and enhancing dermal delivery of *C. asiatica* phytoconstituents. Liposomes, composed of phospholipid bilayers, facilitate the delivery of lipophilic compounds such as asiatic acid while maintaining skin hydration and reducing transepidermal water loss (Liu et al. 2020; Witkowska et al. 2023). Thermoresponsive and graphene oxide-integrated liposomal hydrogels have demonstrated additional functionalities such as electrostimulation responsiveness and scar reduction (Zheng et al. 2020). Niosomes, formed from nonionic surfactants and often surface-modified with hyaluronic acid, have been optimized for enhanced skin deposition. Formulations incorporating asiaticoside showed improved stability, sustained release, and deep epidermal delivery (Hnin et al. 2024; Wichayapreechar et al. 2020). Phytosomes, complexing polar bioactives such as madecassoside with phospholipids, offer enhanced anti-inflammatory action and better skin permeation, as demonstrated by the inhibition of NF- κ B, COX-2, iNOS, and IgE in dermatitis models (Park et al. 2017). Transfersomes, known for their ultra-deformable membranes, have shown the highest transdermal efficiency among vesicular systems. Topical gels containing asiatic acid-loaded transfersomes significantly improved skin hydration and elasticity and reduced melanin levels in hypertrophic scar models, supported by early clinical trials (Opatha et al. 2024).

Lipid-based nanocarriers and nanoemulsions

Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs), nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs), nanoemulgels, and solid lipid microparticles (SLMs) have been extensively utilized to encapsulate *C. asiatica* actives. These sub-100 nm systems protect unstable compounds from degradation and improve their dermal bioavailability. NLCs containing asiaticoside penetrated the stratum corneum more effectively than free extracts, yielding a 50–60% increase in biological activity – especially in collagen stimulation and wound contraction

(da Rocha et al. 2019; Kim et al. 2021; Krzyżostan et al. 2024). Similarly, nanoemulsion formulations based on asiatic acid and natural oils (e.g., virgin coconut oil) achieved near-complete wound closure within 20 days (Mahadev et al. 2025). SLMs, tailored for acne treatment, improved asiatic acid stability and showed controlled release and anti-acne effects in vitro and in vivo (Chutoprapat et al. 2024). These systems are notable for their GRAS-compliant components and scalable manufacturing potential in cosmeceuticals.

Microneedle patches

Microneedle (MN) arrays fabricated from biodegradable polymers such as chitosan or *Bletilla striata* represent a transformative technology for transdermal *C. asiatica* delivery. These arrays bypass the stratum corneum and deliver bioactives directly into the dermis with minimal discomfort (Ryall et al. 2022). Recent studies showed that asiaticoside-loaded dissolvable MNs downregulated TGF- β 1 and COL1 expression, supporting scarless wound healing (Lv et al. 2023). Additionally, 3D-printed MNs containing madecassoside offer targeted dermal therapy for localized dermatologic indications (He et al. 2025). This delivery method is particularly promising for regenerative and anti-aging applications where deeper tissue penetration is required.

Silica-based and other nanocomposites

Nanocomposites utilizing inorganic matrices such as porous silica or metal oxides are increasingly used to stabilize *C. asiatica* compounds and enable targeted dermal effects. Ebau et al. (2023) developed a silica-based nanocomposite that preserved antioxidant activity and protected keratinocytes from oxidative stress – an essential mechanism in anti-aging therapy. Similar formulations with ZnO or magnetic oxides demonstrated antimicrobial, antioxidant, and angiogenic effects in diabetic wound and fungal models (Wang et al. 2024; Sahara et al. 2025). While these systems show promise, long-term dermatological safety and regulatory pathways remain areas for further investigation.

Safety and toxicological profile

C. asiatica is widely regarded as safe and well tolerated for both topical and oral use, supported by its long-standing inclusion in traditional medicine and cosmeceutical formulations. Nevertheless, systematic safety evaluation remains critical, particularly in high-concentration extracts, nanoformulations, and prolonged-use topical products targeting sensitive or compromised skin. Adverse reactions to topical *C. asiatica* are rare and typically mild. The

most frequently reported event is allergic contact dermatitis, though the incidence remains low – generally <1% in published clinical trials (Seo et al. 2025). In a randomized controlled trial evaluating scar treatment creams, only two mild cases of dermatitis were reported: one in the Centella-based cream group and one in the placebo group. Subsequent analysis attributed both reactions to preservative excipients rather than the extract itself (Ratz-Lyko 2016).

Importantly, *C. asiatica* is not considered a common allergen. A recent literature review confirmed only a few documented cases of sensitization despite its widespread global use. In Human Repeat Insult Patch Test (HRIPT) protocols involving 100 volunteers over 21 days, formulations containing *C. asiatica* extracts did not induce significant irritation or sensitization in the majority of participants (Korkina et al. 2024). This supports its designation as a low-risk botanical, although caution is advised for individuals with known sensitivities to herbal or plant-based ingredients. Unlike retinoids or alpha-hydroxy acids, *C. asiatica* does not typically cause photosensitivity or epidermal thinning. On the contrary, it is often employed to repair the skin barrier and manage irritant dermatitis, making it particularly suitable for rosacea-prone or post-procedure skin. For instance, a study utilizing a *C. asiatica*-infused facial mask for rosacea management reported improved barrier integrity, reduced flare-ups, and no adverse events (Kim et al. 2021).

However, new-generation delivery systems such as liposomes, nanofibers, hydrogels, and microneedles can alter the dermal absorption kinetics of *C. asiatica* constituents. While these systems enhance efficacy, they also necessitate updated toxicological screening. Current studies report no enhanced irritation with such vehicles. For instance, HRIPT and patch testing of chitosan-based microneedles and graphene oxide liposomal gels did not elicit adverse dermal responses in animal models or preliminary human use (Ryall et al. 2022; Zheng et al. 2020). According to the Cosmetic Ingredient Review (CIR 2023) and European SCCS opinions, *C. asiatica* derivative ingredients are safe to use in cosmetic formulations as long as impurities and contaminants are controlled.

Conclusion

This review synthesizes emerging evidence supporting *C. asiatica* as a multifunctional dermatological agent with wide-ranging applications in skin regeneration, inflammation control, and cosmetic repair. Across delivery systems and biological models, the plant's therapeutic effects are consistently linked to its core triterpenoid components, including asiaticoside, madecassoside, asiatic acid, and madecassic acid, which target multiple cellular pathways such as TGF- β /Smad, Wnt/ β -catenin, and NF- κ B. This multitarget mechanism positions *C. asiatica* as an attractive candidate for conditions requiring simultaneous modulation of inflammation, matrix remodeling, and epidermal regeneration.

Lipid-based nanocarriers, such as solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs), nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs), and nanoemulsions, have emerged as the most versatile systems. They consistently enhanced bioavailability and stability, achieving 50–60% greater collagen-stimulatory activity compared to nonencapsulated extracts. These carriers also facilitated deeper dermal penetration without irritation – an important differentiator for anti-aging and sensitive-skin formulations.

Advanced vesicular systems, including liposomes, niosomes, phytosomes, and transfersomes, have addressed the plant's limited skin permeability. Transfersomes, in particular, demonstrated high transdermal efficiency and clinical efficacy in hypertrophic scar treatment, outperforming conventional formulations in improving elasticity and pigmentation. Niosomal and liposomal systems further facilitated sustained dermal retention of asiaticoside, often enhanced by surfactant modifications or hyaluronic acid coating (Hnin et al. 2024; Liu et al. 2020). Phytosome complexes showed added anti-inflammatory effects in atopic and contact dermatitis models, emphasizing the importance of delivery vehicle–bioactive interactions.

From a safety perspective, *C. asiatica* maintains an excellent tolerability profile. Contact dermatitis and sensitization are rare, with most adverse events attributed to formulation excipients rather than the extract itself. HRIPT and patch test studies show minimal irritation even in sensitive skin, contrasting favorably with conventional actives such as retinoids or hydroxy acids. Despite these strengths, clinical evidence remains somewhat fragmented. Most trials are small, short-term, and lack direct comparators. While preclinical models robustly support efficacy in wound healing and inflammation, longer-term human trials – particularly for anti-aging and pigmentation – are needed. Future research should emphasize extended clinical trials with clear regulatory guidelines and more innovative strategies.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declare that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declare that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declare that no informed consent was obtained from humans, donors, or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declare that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declare that no commercially available immortalized human or animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

We disclose that artificial intelligence tools were used only to assist in language refinement and grammatical clarity. All content was critically reviewed and verified by the authors to ensure accuracy and integrity.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

RH and RMF: Writing – review and editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization; MM and AYC: Writing – review and editing, Supervi-

sion. All authors have critically reviewed the findings and approved the final manuscript.

Author ORCIDs

Retty Handayani <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9560-3490>
 Raden Maya Febriyanti <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3437-3011>
 Muhaimin Muhaimin <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6269-5931>
 Anis Yohana Chearunisaa <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4985-8206>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

References

- Alam MN, Marney L, Yang L, Choi J, Cerruti N, Techen N, Bassett S, Smith J, Brown K, Cabey K, Viswanathan R, Rajagopal S, Soumyanath A, Stevens JE, Maier CS (2025) Clustering of chemical profiles of *Centella asiatica* cultivars, grown in greenhouses, allows grouping of metabolites with similar production trends. *Industrial Crops and Products* 231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2025.121159>
- Arribas-López E, Zand N, Ojo O, Snowden MJ, Kochhar T (2022) A systematic review of the effect of *Centella asiatica* on wound healing. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19(6): e3266. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19063266>
- Balevi M, Balevi A (2023) The effect of *Centella asiatica* cream on scar development in patients who underwent open carpal tunnel release surgery. *Journal of Hand Therapy* 36: 962–966. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jht.2022.11.001>
- Bansal K, Bhati H, Vanshita, Bajpai M (2024) Recent insights into therapeutic potential and nanostructured carrier systems of *Centella asiatica*: An evidence-based review. *Pharmacological Research – Modern Chinese Medicine* 10: e100403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prmcm.2024.100403>
- Bisht VK, Bhandari AK, Bisht RS, Kandari LS, Chandra S, Negi T, Palai S, Rosas JF, Junior JJ, e Silva DA, Coutinho HDM (2024) HPLC analysis and antibacterial activity of methanolic extract of *Centella asiatica* (L.) urban. *Pharmacological Research – Natural Products* 5: e100106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prenap.2024.100106>
- Borges ALS, Bittar VP, Justino AB, Carrillo MSP, Duarte RFM, Silva NBS, Gonçalves DS, Prado DG, Araújo IAC, Martins MM, Motata LC, Martins CHG, Botelho FV, Silva NM, de Oliveira A, Romão W, Espíndola FS (2024) Exploring the composition and properties of *Centella asiatica* metabolites and investigating their impact on BSA glycation, LDL oxidation and α – amylase inhibition. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis* 245: e116143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2024.116143>
- Bozkaya O, Arat E, Gün Gök Z, Yiğitoğlu M, Vargel İ (2022) Production and characterization of hybrid nanofiber wound dressing containing *Centella asiatica* coated silver nanoparticles by mutual electrospinning method. *European Polymer Journal* 166: e111023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2022.111023>
- Chutoprapat R, Witarat J, Jongpanyangarm P, Mang Sung Thluai L, Khankaew P, Wah Chan L (2024) Development of solid lipid micro-particles (SLMs) containing asiatic acid for topical treatment of acne: Characterization, stability, in vitro and in vivo anti-acne assessment. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics* 654: e123980. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2024.123980>
- Dang Y-y, Liu T, Liu Y-d, Li J-y, Jing Y, Yang M-j, Zhang H, Jiang M-m, Wu H-h, Yang W-z, Li N, Zhang P (2024) Anti-photoaging activity of triterpenoids isolated from *Centella asiatica*. *Phytochemistry* 228: e114246. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytochem.2024.114246>
- Diniz LRL, Calado LL, Duarte ABS, de Sousa DP (2023) *Centella asiatica* and Its metabolite asiatic acid. Wound Healing Effects and Therapeutic Potential. *Metabolites* 13(2): e276. <https://doi.org/10.3390/metabo13020276>
- Ebau F, Scano A, Manca ML, Manconi M, Cabras V, Pilloni M, Ennas G (2023) *Centella asiatica* extract-SiO₂ nanocomposite: More than a drug-delivery system for skin protection from oxidative damage. *Journal of Biomedical Materials Research – Part A* 111: 300–308. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbm.a.37462>
- Gayathri K, Abhinand PA, Gayathri V, Prasanna Lakshmi V, Chamundeeswari D, Jiang L, Tian Z, Malathi N (2024) Computational analysis of phytochemicals in *Centella asiatica* for its antifibrotic and drug-likeness properties – Herb to drug study. *Heliyon* 10(13): e33762. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e33762>
- He Y, He D, Ren S, Fan L, Wang L, Sun J (2025) 3D-printed microneedles loaded with madecassoside for periodontal soft tissue regeneration. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics* 676: e125569. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2025.125569>
- Hein ZM, Gopalakrishna PK, Kanuri AK, Thomas W, Hussan F, Naik VR, Shantakumari N, Che Ramli MD, Mohd Moklas MA, Che Mohd Nassir CMN, Vishnumukkala T (2025) *Centella asiatica*: Advances in Extraction Technologies, Phytochemistry, and Therapeutic Applications. *Life* 15: e1081. <https://doi.org/10.3390/life15071081>
- Hnin HM, Tun T, Jansook P (2024) Development and validation of high-performance liquid chromatography method for the simultaneous quantification of rivastigmine hydrogen tartrate and asiaticoside co-loaded in niosomes: A Box–Behnken design approach. *Journal of Chromatography B: Analytical Technologies in the Biomedical and Life Sciences* 1241: e124170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jchromb.2024.124170>
- Jiang H, Zhou X, Chen L (2022) Asiaticoside delays senescence and attenuate generation of ROS in UV-exposure cells through regulates

- TGF- β 1/Smad pathway. *Experimental and Therapeutic Medicine* 24(5). <https://doi.org/10.3892/etm.2022.11603>
- Johnson W, Bergfeld WF, Belsito DV, Hill RA, Klaassen CD, Liebler DC, Marks JG, Shank RC, Slaga TJ, Snyder PW, Gill LJ, Heldreth B (2023) Safety assessment of *Centella asiatica* – Derived ingredients as used in cosmetics. *International Journal of Toxicology* 42: 5S–22S. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10915818231158272>
- Khalili Hassanabadi M, Mirjalili MH, Mohajeri M (2025) Boosted centellosides production in Gotu kola (*Centella asiatica*) transgenic hairy roots elicited by gold and zinc nanoparticles. *Industrial Crops and Products* 227: e120796. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2025.120796>
- Kim EA, Park JS, Kim MS, Jeong MY, Park HJ, Choi JH, Seo JH, Choi YS, Kang MJ (2021) High-payload nanosuspension of *Centella asiatica* extract for improved skin delivery with no irritation. *International Journal of Nanomedicine* 16: 7417–7432. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJN.S335039>
- Korkina L, Kharaeva Z, Shokarova A, Barokova E, Mayer W, Trakhtman I, Dal Toso R, De Luca C (2024) Effects of plant meristem-cell-based cosmetics on menopausal skin: Clinical data and mechanisms. *Biomolecules* 14(9): e1176. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom14091176>
- Kunjumon R, Johnson AJ, Baby S (2022) *Centella asiatica*: Secondary metabolites, biological activities and biomass sources. *Phytomedicine Plus* 2(1): e100176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phyplu.2021.100176>
- Kunjumon R, Viswanathan G, Baby S (2024) Potential of asiaticoside encapsulated alginate chitosan nanoparticles in the management of antiproliferative activity in C6 glioma cells. *Brain Behavior and Immunity Integrative* 5: e100043. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbi.2023.100043>
- Li L, Liu L, Wang T (2025) Effects of asiaticosides on scar recovery and psychological well-being in patients with scald injuries. *Pharmacognosy Magazine* 21(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/09731296241312483>
- Liu M, Chen W, Zhang X, Su P, Yue F, Zeng S, Du S (2020) Improved surface adhesion and wound healing effect of madecassoside liposomes modified by temperature-responsive PEG-PCL-PEG copolymers. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 151: e105373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejps.2020.105373>
- Liu S, Zhao Y, Li M, Nie L, Wei Q, Okoro OV, Jafari H, Wang S, Deng J, Chen J, Shavandi A, Fan L (2023) Bioactive wound dressing based on decellularized tendon and GelMA with incorporation of PDA-loaded asiaticoside nanoparticles for scarless wound healing. *Chemical Engineering Journal* 466: e143016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2023.143016>
- Mahadev M, Ballal S, Shetty A, Dubey A, Shetty SS, Hebbar S, El-Zahaby SA (2025) Development and evaluation of chitosan-coated virgin coconut oil-asiatic acid-loaded nanoemulgel for enhanced wound management. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules* 299: e140097. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2025.140097>
- Manotham S, Khieokae M, Butnoi P (2023) Electrospun biopolymer polyvinyl alcohol/*Centella asiatica* extract nanofibers for antibacterial activity. *Materials Today: Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2023.06.166>
- Masi F, Chianese G, Peterlongo F, Riva A, Tagliatalata-Scafati O (2022) Phytochemical profile of Centevita, a *Centella asiatica* leaves extract, and isolation of a new oleanane-type saponin. *Fitoterapia* 158: e105163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fitote.2022.105163>
- Mohapatra P, Ray A, Jena S, Nayak S, Mohanty S (2021) Influence of extraction methods and solvent system on the chemical composition and antioxidant activity of *Centella asiatica* L. leaves. *Biocatalysis and Agricultural Biotechnology* 33: e101971. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bcab.2021.101971>
- Narisepalli S, Salunkhe SA, Chitkara D, Mittal A (2023) Asiaticoside polymeric nanoparticles for effective diabetic wound healing through increased collagen biosynthesis: In-vitro and in-vivo evaluation. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics* 631: e122508. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2022.122508>
- Opatha SAT, Chutoprapat R, Khankaew P, Titapiwatanakun V, Ruk-siriwanich W, Boonpisuttinant K (2024) Asiatic acid-entrapped transfersomes for the treatment of hypertrophic scars: *In vitro* appraisal, bioactivity evaluation, and clinical study. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics* 651: e123738. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2023.123738>
- Park HS, Shin S (2025) Clinical efficacy and safety evaluation of a *Centella asiatica* (CICA)- derived extracellular vesicle formulation for anti-aging skincare. *Cosmetics* 12: e135. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cosmetics12040135>
- Park JH, Choi JY, Son DJ, Park EK, Song MJ, Hellström M, Hong JT (2017) Anti-inflammatory effect of titrated extract of *Centella asiatica* in phthalic anhydride-induced allergic dermatitis animal model. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 18(4): e738. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms18040738>
- Park KS (2021) Pharmacological effects of *Centella asiatica* on skin diseases: Evidence and possible mechanisms. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine* 462633: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/5462633>
- Poomanee W, Yaowiwat N, Pattarachaidacharuch T, Leelapornpisid P (2023) Optimized multiherbal combination and in vivo anti-skin aging potential: a randomized double blind placebo controlled study. *Scientific Reports* 13(5633). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-32738-7>
- Rashid MdH-O-, Akter MstM, Uddin J, Islam S, Rahman M, Jahan K, Sarker MdMR, Sadik G (2023) Antioxidant, cytotoxic, antibacterial and thrombolytic activities of *Centella asiatica* L.: possible role of phenolics and flavonoids. *Clinical Phytoscience* 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40816-023-00353-8>
- Ratz-Lyko A, Arct J, Pytkowska K (2016) Moisturizing and anti-inflammatory properties of cosmetic formulations containing *Centella asiatica* extract. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 78(1): 27–33. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0250-474X.180247>
- da Rocha PBR, Souza B dos S, Andrade LM, dos Anjos JL V, Mendanha SA, Alonso A, Marreto RN, Taveira SF (2019) Enhanced asiaticoside skin permeation by *Centella asiatica*-loaded lipid nanoparticles: Effects of extract type and study of stratum corneum lipid dynamics. *Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology* 50: 305–312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jddst.2019.01.016>
- Ryall C, Chen S, Duarah S, Wen J (2022) Chitosan-based microneedle arrays for dermal delivery of *Centella asiatica*. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics* 627: e122221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2022.122221>
- Sahara FA, Sultana MS, Amin MK, Shamim Al Mamun M, Dhar PK, Dutta SK (2025) One-pot synthesis and characterization of magnetic α -Fe₂O₃/CuO/CuFe₂O₄ nanocomposite for multifunctional Therapeutic Applications. *ChemistryOpen* 14(2): e202400277. <https://doi.org/10.1002/open.202400277>
- Seo J, Jeong C, Oh SM, Lee S-Y, Park HW, Seo DB, Yoo DS, Sim W-J, Lim T-G, Yoon Park JH, Lee CH, Lee KW (2024) Giant *Centella asiatica*, a novel cultivar rich in madecassoside and asiaticoside, suppresses α -melanocyte-stimulating hormone-induced melanogenesis

- through MC1R binding. *International Journal of Molecular Medicine* 55(1): 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3892/ijmm.2024.5454>
- Shen X, Guo M, Yu H, Liu D, Lu Z, Lu Y (2019) *Propionibacterium acnes* related anti- inflammation and skin hydration activities of madecassoside, a pentacyclic triterpene saponin from *Centella asiatica*. *Bio-science, Biotechnology and Biochemistry* 83: 561–568. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09168451.2018.1547627>
- Shin HY, Kim H, Jung S, Jeong EJ, Lee KH, Bae YJ, Suh HJ, Jang K Il, Yu KW (2021) Interrelationship between secondary metabolites and antioxidant capacities of *Centella asiatica* using bivariate and multivariate correlation analyses. *Applied Biological Chemistry* 64. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13765-021-00656-9>
- Singh SP, Misra A, Kumar B, Adhikari D, Srivastava S, Barik SK (2022) Identification of potential cultivation areas for centelloside-specific elite chemotypes of *Centella asiatica* (L.) using ecological niche modeling. *Industrial Crops and Products* 188: e115657. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2022.115657>
- Singh R, Kharsyntiew B, Sharma P, Sahoo UK, Sarangi PK, Prus P, Imbrea F (2023) The effect of production and post-harvest processing practices on quality attributes in *Centella asiatica* (L.) Urban – A review. *Agronomy* 13(8): e1999. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy13081999>
- Soun-udom M, Garcia MR, Oliveira AP, Andrade PB, Vajrodaya S, Duangsrisai S, Gomes NGM (2024) LED light treatments enhance neuroprotective properties and differentially impact phenolic compounds and triterpenoid content in Gotu Kola (*Centella asiatica* (L.) Urb.). *Current Plant Biology* 40: e100386. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpb.2024.100386>
- Suhail M, Chiu IH, Ullah A, Khan A, Ullah H, Al-Sowayan NS, Wu PC (2024) Formulation and in vitro assessment of polymeric pH-Responsive nanogels of chitosan for sustained delivery of madecassoside. *ACS Omega* 9: 19345–19352. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.4c00461>
- Sun B, Wu L, Wu Y, Zhang C, Qin L, Hayashi M, Kudo M, Gao M, Liu T (2020) Therapeutic potential of *Centella asiatica* and its triterpenes: A review. *Frontiers in Pharmacology* 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2020.568032>
- Tai M, He Q, Lv P, Li W, Ling X, Li L, Guo M (2025) Madecassoside alleviates PM2.5-induced skin cell damage. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications* 770: e151977. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbrc.2025.151977>
- Thanusha AV, Dinda AK, Koul V (2018) Evaluation of nano hydrogel composite based on gelatin/HA/CS suffused with Asiatic acid/ZnO and CuO nanoparticles for second degree burns. *Materials Science and Engineering C* 89: 378–386. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2018.03.034>
- Tripathy S, Srivastav PP (2023) Encapsulation of *Centella asiatica* leaf extract in liposome: Study on structural stability, degradation kinetics and fate of bioactive compounds during storage. *Food Chemistry Advances* 2: e100202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.focha.2023.100202>
- Vajpayee D, Parashar AK, Sethi VA (2024) Design and development of topical hydrogel of *Centella asiatica* for the treatment of skin burn. *International Journal of Newgen Research in Pharmacy & Healthcare*: 229–234. <https://doi.org/10.61554/ijnrph.v2i1.2024.62>
- Vasavi HS, Arun AB, Rekha PD (2016) Anti-quorum sensing activity of flavonoid-rich fraction from *Centella asiatica* L. against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* PAO1. *Journal of Microbiology, Immunology and Infection* 49: 8–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmii.2014.03.012>
- Wang L, Yang Y, Han W, Ding H (2024) Novel design and development of *Centella Asiatica* extract – loaded poloxamer/ZnO nanocomposite wound closure material to improve anti- bacterial action and enhanced wound healing efficacy in diabetic foot ulcer. *Regenerative Therapy* 27: 92–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reth.2024.03.006>
- Wichayapreechar P, Anuchapreeda S, Phongpradist R, Rungseewijitprapa W, Ampasavate C (2020) Dermal targeting of *Centella asiatica* extract using hyaluronic acid surface modified liposomes. *Journal of Liposome Research* 30: 197–207. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08982104.2019.1614952>
- Witkowska K, Paczkowska-Walendowska M, Plech T, Szymanowska D, Michniak-Kohn B, Cielecka-Piontek J (2023) Chitosan-based hydrogels for controlled delivery of asiaticoside-rich *Centella asiatica* extracts with wound healing potential. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 24(24): e17229. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms242417229>
- Witkowska K, Paczkowska-Walendowska M, Miklaszewski A, Plech T, Michniak-Kohn B, Swora-Cwynar E, Cielecka-Piontek J (2025) Development of 3D-Printed chitosan-based hydrogels rich in *Centella asiatica* extract for enhanced wound healing applications. *Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology* 111: e107143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jddst.2025.107143>
- Wu J, Xu G, Zhou X, Wan J, Liao H, Li C, Shi Y, Wen H (2025) Asiatic acid inhibits keloid fibroblast migration and collagen deposition via suppression of STAT3 activation. *Burns*: e107586. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.burns.2025.107586>
- Zeng W, Li H, Liu S, Luo Z, Chen J, Zhou J (2025) Biosynthesis and bioactivities of triterpenoids from *Centella asiatica*: Challenges and opportunities. *Biotechnology Advances* 80: e108541. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotechadv.2025.108541>
- Zhang G, Liu Z, Li Z, Xu Y (2024) Future directions about keloid scars based on pathogenesis and therapies. *Clinical, Cosmetic and Investigational Dermatology* 17: 2391–2408. <https://doi.org/10.2147/CCID.S470650>
- Zhao J, Shi J, Shan Y, Yu M, Zhu X, Zhu Y, Liu L, Sheng M (2020) Asiaticoside inhibits TGF- β 1-induced mesothelial-mesenchymal transition and oxidative stress via the Nrf2/HO-1 signaling pathway in the human peritoneal mesothelial cell line HMrSV5. *Cellular and Molecular Biology Letters* 25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s11658-020-00226-9>
- Zheng F, Li R, He Q, Koral K, Tao J, Fan L, Xiang R, Ma J, Wang N, Yin Y, Huang Z, Xu P, Xu H (2020) The electrostimulation and scar inhibition effect of chitosan/oxidized hydroxyethyl cellulose/reduced graphene oxide/asiaticoside liposome based hydrogel on peripheral nerve regeneration in vitro. *Materials Science and Engineering C* 109: e110560. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2019.110560>

Supplementary material 1

Search Strategy

Authors: Retty Handayani, Raden Maya Febriyanti, Muhaimin Muhaimin, Anis Yohana Chearunisaa

Data type: docx

Explanation note: **fig. S1.** Number of *Centella asiatica* dermatology and cosmeceutics publications cited in the review by publication year (2016–2025).

Copyright notice: This dataset is made available under the Open Database License (<http://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/1.0>). The Open Database License (ODbL) is a license agreement intended to allow users to freely share, modify, and use this Dataset while maintaining this same freedom for others, provided that the original source and author(s) are credited.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e167217.suppl1>